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Renaissance, Exploring the ‘New World’

Nazia

Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
Government General Degree College, Mangalkote,
Affiliated to the University of Burdwan, W.B.

Dr. Imrul Kayes Alam Sarkar

Assistant Professor and Head,
Department of English,
Sailajananda Falguni Smriti Mahavidyalaya,
Affiliated to the University of Burdwan, W.B.

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Abstract:

The present paper aims to show how the Renaissance brought a great leap forward in different types of knowledge and it highlights how the Renaissance led to the opening of new trade, the conquest of foreign territories and the founding of colonies. During that time, religious and economic motives played an important part in the process of exploration. Besides these, political ambition was also a significant force that enhanced exploration. Finally, this paper elaborates on different perspectives and outcomes of the Renaissance and it explores how Renaissance chronicles are characterized by the imposition of European images and values onto an unfamiliar world.

Keywords: Renaissance, Knowledge, Exploration and Expansion.

During the Middle Ages, Europeans knew little about the world beyond their lands and the seas around them. The Renaissance brought a great leap forward in geographic knowledge and interest in the rest of the globe. Beginning in the 1400s, Europeans made a series of remarkable voyages to Africa, Asia, the Americas, and the Pacific Ocean. This exploration led to the opening of new trade, the conquest of foreign territories, and the founding of colonies. From these colonies grew the overseas empires of Portugal, Spain, the Netherlands, Britain, and France.

The mid-to-late fifteenth century has been called the Age of Exploration and Discovery. It was an age in which driven by economic, religious, and political forces European sailors left the coastal waters of the Old World to embark on overseas adventure. First, Portuguese ships, then Spanish and finally, in the late fifteenth and early sixteenth centuries, British, French and Dutch ships set out to discover a world beyond known territory, a "New World".

European exploration during the Renaissance grew out of various motives and factors. One was simple curiosity, the growing interest in the world that was a key feature of the dawning Renaissance. The legacy of the Roman and Ancient Greek civilisations that had regular trading and diplomatic contact with India and China inspired the Europeans of the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries to attempt to establish their own eastern empires. Alexander the Great's empire, for example, consisted of territories in both Greece and India. Links between the Europeans and the Asians were disrupted by barbarian conquests in China, India, and Europe in the fourth and fifth centuries C.E. In the eighth century Islam engulfed North Africa, the Eastern Mediterranean, Spain, and France, igniting hostilities between the Christian and Muslim kingdoms that led to the cutoff of trade routes to the East. In the early Middle Ages, the greatest

contributions to an increased knowledge of the world were made by the Vikings, or Norsemen. From around the year 1000 they were active in exploring North America, and their voyages there are recorded until the middle of the fourteenth century. For centuries Europe's only knowledge of the East was limited and often second-hand. Among Christian travelers in the Middle Ages, the greatest was Marco Polo, a member of the Venetian merchant aristocracy, who spent over twenty years in the East, seventeen of them in the service of Kublai Khan, ruler of the great Mongol Empire in Asia. After Polo's return to Europe in 1295, he wrote a book to describe what he had seen and heard. Merchants like Marco Polo, gleaned valuable information about the East while looking for new trade routes. Europeans were so inspired by travelling accounts like Marco Polo's, that they were determined to re-establish routes of their own to the riches of the East.

Economic motives played a key role as well. Most of the explorers had the immediate task of finding a direct route to India and the Far East in order to obtain spices such as pepper, cinnamon, nutmeg, ginger and cloves. Although Europe was, by and large, a self-sustaining continent, Europeans had acquired a taste for luxury items that had long been traded from the East (Persia, India, China, etc.) and whose demand far exceeded the supply since 1250. The lure of profits from the cotton, silk, precious stones, exotic spices, and slaves that were traded prompted Europeans to find a better way to directly access these items. European and Eastern traders had established overland routes through central Asia that served as direct links for these exotic goods, but even regional overland trade was risky and costly. Moreover, when the city of Constantinople fell to the Ottoman Turks in 1453, the overland trade route to the East was disrupted. Thus the European demand for luxury goods fueled the search for a sea route to Asia.

Religion also played a part in the growth of exploration. Vasco da Gama was said to have named "Christians and spices" as the objects of his voyage to India. The desire to convert was linked to the crusading zeal, which lived on in the hearts of many Portuguese and Spanish as a legacy of their long conflicts with the Moors. To combine a profitable acquisition of new trade routes with a telling blow against the infidel was a potent combination in urging brave men on to daring enterprises. The "New World" and its "heathen" population challenged and inspired the Roman Catholic Church to fulfil its self-proclaimed destiny of being the one universal faith of humanity. As God's representative on Earth the Pope provided the moral authority that legitimised European exploration and subsequent exploitation of new territory. For example, in 1452, Pope Nicholas V issued a papal bull allowing the enslavement of "pagans and infidels" justifying all European slaving expeditions to Africa. In order to spread Christ's message to "heathen" masses while protecting the Church's sovereignty over the new territories, the Church sent missionaries to accompany many of the voyages of overseas expansion. The Church eventually granted kingdoms like Portugal and Spain political sovereignty over these territories, clearly establishing the Church's ultimate authority in European society.

Finally, political ambition was an important force that propelled exploration. Some European rulers who sponsored voyages wanted to gather allies to fight the growth of the Muslim empire. During this time a shift in European life from the Mediterranean to the Atlantic coastline was discernable. Leadership in European political and economic life was coming more and more into the hands of Portugal, Spain, France, and England. These nations all had monarchies that were growing in strength, increasing their control over the various classes within the state, and consolidating their hold over the territories subject to them. They all had Atlantic coastlines, and led the way in seeking new trade routes and new lands. The Dutch joined in the race as their

political independence grew. These rising states sought a way to counteract the long-standing Italian particularly Venetian monopoly of the eastern trade. European nations that discovered new territories could acquire great riches, power, and prestige through trade and colonial outposts.

Some historians argue that new techniques and tools of shipbuilding and navigation launched a wave of ambitious voyages. However, before this time, three practical problems would have discouraged Europeans from sailing beyond the familiar Mediterranean Sea or the Atlantic coast. The problems involved maps, navigation, and ships. First, mariners lacked maps and charts of foreign waters and possessed little useful knowledge of winds and currents. The only way to gather information and create maps was through voyages of discovery. Charting unfamiliar shores would be one of the great accomplishments of Renaissance explorers.

Second, mariners did not have much experience sailing out of sight of land, and their navigational tools and methods were primitive. They had crude compasses but did not really understand the differences between magnetic north and true north until the 1500s. They could measure latitude with instruments called astrolabes and quadrants, but using these instruments aboard moving ships was difficult. As the age of exploration progressed, sailors devised more efficient methods of measuring latitude. However, the accurate measurement of longitude at sea did not occur until the 1700s.

Third, few ships were well equipped for long ocean voyages or unfavorable winds. Explorers in the early 1400s used caravels—small, triangular-sailed ships built for coastal cruising. Over time, Atlantic sailors adapted caravels to handle square sails as well, making them better suited to wind conditions on the high seas. As voyages became longer, the need for bigger storage areas

led to the development of a larger ship called the carrack. By 1500 carracks might be as much as four times as large as caravels.

Solutions to the problems of maps, navigation, and ships arose during, not before, the age of exploration. Thus, the Europeans of the early Renaissance pushed out into the unknown with inadequate equipment from the past and the need for more accurate maps and skilled mapmakers led to great developments in the art and science of cartography in the fifteenth century.

Although the so-called Age of Discovery began in the late fifteenth century, Europeans had been probing the known areas and boundaries of their world for several centuries before that, motivated by tales of fabulous riches in distant kingdoms in Africa and Asia. Christian missionaries and leaders of the Catholic Church in Rome had also sent emissaries into Asia in the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries to spread the message of Christianity. Developments in the mid-fifteenth century added momentum to those efforts. At about the same time, the invention of movable type (associated with Johannes Gutenberg) made it possible to reproduce written materials more cheaply and quickly. Reports on great events such as the fall of Constantinople, ancient treatises about geography and real or fanciful books about travel, inspired many Europeans to seek new venues for trade, spread the message of Christianity, and search for allies against Ottoman expansion.

Initially, exploration took the form of small-scale ventures that were financed by independent businessmen. Potential explorers sought out investors among wealthy merchant communities, and asked for sponsorship from the monarchies. Some were members of the nobility like Prince Henry, and others were members of the merchant class. These early ventures took the form of raid and trade excursions. Ships were sent along the coast of Africa to find inhabited areas where

Europeans could trade or raid goods and slaves. These early independent excursions by merchants and adventurers proved that exploration was profitable and eventually European monarchs began to take a greater interest. Thus exploration evolved from cautious, small-scale operations to a systematic approach that incorporated royal patronage, substantial capital and long-range planning. The Iberian kingdoms of Portugal and Spain were early pioneers that sponsored numerous voyages of exploration. The Portuguese focused primarily on a trading empire while the Spanish sought a territorial empire they could colonise.

Historians date the great age of exploration from 1415, when a Portuguese prince named Dom Henry helped capture Ceuta, a Muslim city in North Africa. This adventure inspired the prince, later called Henry the Navigator (1394–1460), to sponsor a series of voyages of exploration. Over the next century, such expeditions would eventually bring Portugal colonies in Africa, Asia, and South America. In 1419 Henry began outfitting ships for missions into the Atlantic. Some of these voyages led to the establishment of colonies on the islands of Madeira and the Canaries. Other expeditions probed southward along the west coast of Africa. By 1434 one of the prince's navigators had passed Cape Bojador, the southernmost point reached by Europeans. In a series of voyages from 1444 to 1460, the Portuguese found the mouth of the Senegal River, explored the Cape Verde Islands, and reached Sierra Leone. During that period, they began trading with Africans along the coast for ivory, gold dust, and slaves. By the time of Henry's death, Portuguese mariners had made at least 35 voyages to western Africa. Historians debate how many of these journeys Henry directly sponsored, but clearly he played the leading role in the nation's drive to explore other lands.

After Henry's death, a succession of Portuguese kings sponsored voyages along the African coast to the mouth of the Congo River and beyond. These expeditions resulted in increased trade in gold, pepper, and slaves. The voyages raised questions about the geography of Africa that led Portuguese king John II (ruled 1481–1495) to launch several expeditions in 1487. One group of explorers traveled through land in search of a route across Africa. Others went to India to learn about the commerce and navigation of the Indian Ocean. Most importantly, Bartolomeu Dias sailed off to find the southern tip of Africa and a route around it. In 1488 Dias returned to Portugal and reported that he had rounded the tip of Africa, which the king named the Cape of Good Hope. These trips produced two valuable pieces of information: that ships could sail around Africa and that regular commerce existed between eastern Africa and India across the northern Indian Ocean.

Nearly nine years passed before another Portuguese expedition set out to take advantage of these discoveries. In 1497 Vasco da Gama left Portugal with four ships. The fleet rounded the Cape of Good Hope and stopped at several ports in eastern Africa before landing on the coast of India. Gama returned to Portugal in 1499, having found the basic sea route that would open to Europeans the trade of India and the Asian lands beyond. About six months later, a much larger fleet under the command of Pedro Álvares Cabral sailed from Portugal for India. However, on the way the ships were blown westward by storms and ended up on the coast of Brazil. Cabral claimed the land for Portugal. After a few weeks he resumed his journey, reaching India in September 1500, and he set up several trading posts. Within a few years, other expeditions had built fortified trading posts along the eastern coast of Africa, at the entrances to the Red Sea and the Persian Gulf, and along the shores of the Indian peninsula. The Portuguese also created

settlements farther east, eventually gaining control of the trade of the Spice Islands (now called the Moluccas).

While the Portuguese were opening and exploiting the sea route that led eastward around Africa to the Indian Ocean and Asia, others turned westward. It was the Spanish who rode the second wave of expansion and exploration, but unlike Portugal, Spain founded its empire on conquest and colonization, and not trade. Perhaps the most important of the Spanish endeavors was that of Christopher Columbus (1451-1506). Christopher Columbus hoped to reach Asia by sailing west across the Atlantic Ocean but landed instead in the Americas. His historic voyage across the ocean and back in 1492–1493 was just the beginning of transatlantic exploration.

Columbus made three more voyages, determined to find a passage to the markets of Asia. Even before his death in 1506, however, other navigators had visited the Americas. Although many of them focused their efforts on finding a way through or around the continents to Asia, others were interested in the geography, people, and resources of the uncharted lands. Mapmakers had begun to realize that these lands were part of the world previously unknown to Europeans. As early as 1493 Pietro Martire d'Anghiera, an Italian scholar in Spain, called Columbus's discovery "the New World."

One of the first to venture into that world was John Cabot, an Italian navigator working for England. In 1497 he sailed from Bristol to the island of Newfoundland, now part of Canada. On a second expedition a year later Cabot was lost without a trace. Soon afterward Portuguese mariners explored the region around Newfoundland. Meanwhile, several Portuguese expeditions along the northern and eastern coasts of South America began to reveal the vast size of the

continent. Spanish navigators looked along the coasts of Central America and the Yucatan Peninsula for an easy water passage through the Americas.

Geographers realized that these continents lay between Europe and Asia. It might be possible, however, to sail around the southern tip of South America as the Portuguese had sailed around Africa. In 1519 Portuguese navigator Ferdinand Magellan led an expedition for Spain that would test that idea. Magellan, who believed that a narrow sea separated South America from the Spice Islands (Moluccas) and Asia, managed to find a route through the turbulent waters at the tip of South America and into the Pacific Ocean. Although Magellan had greatly underestimated the distance to Asia, he landed in the Philippines with his fleet after 106 days at sea. Magellan died in the Philippines in 1521, but Juan Sebastián del Cano took command of the remaining ship and returned to Spain in 1522. He was the first navigator to sail around the world. As a result of Magellan's voyage, Spain claimed the Philippines as a colony.

During this first phase of Renaissance exploration, Europeans learned the shape and size of Africa, mapped many Asian islands and coasts, discovered new continents, and established European colonies in the tropics. Many later voyages and expeditions failed to reach their goals but still added to the accumulation of geographic knowledge. Countries like England and France also played active roles in the exploration of the "New World." Rivalries between these powers sustained and advanced exploration as each sought to outstrip the other in terms of raw goods and riches provided by their overseas empires. Thus, every single European institution, from the Church to the average citizen, felt the effects of the voyages of exploration.

One of the most frustrating goals was to find a Northwest Passage, a waterway that would enable ships to sail through North America to the Pacific Ocean. Between 1524 and 1610, Giovanni da

Verrazano and Jacques Cartier for the French, Martin Frobisher and John Davis for the English, and Henry Hudson for the Dutch all tried to find the route and failed. However, Cartier's voyages up the St. Lawrence River launched French exploration and colonization in Canada, and Hudson's voyage into the bay that carries his name led to later expeditions and the establishment of the English fur trade in the region.

Far to the south, stories of legendary golden cities and kingdoms lured explorers. Such rumors drew adventurers such as Walter Raleigh and Francisco Vásquez de Coronado into the interior of South America and the North American southwest. No such cities were found, but each expedition resulted in more information about the American continents. Spanish military leader and conqueror Hernán Cortés and other conquistadors went deep into the interior and captured the fabulously wealthy empires in Mexico and Peru. By the mid-1500s Europeans had some knowledge of all the major river systems of South America and had traced most of the continent's coast.

The mammoth Pacific Ocean was the great unknown. A Spanish expedition meant to follow Magellan's route around the globe ended in disaster in the 1520s. Fifty years later, England's Sir Francis Drake made the second complete trip around the world, pioneering an alternate route around the tip of South America and possibly exploring part of the California coast. Perhaps more significant, though, was the achievement of Spanish navigators Felipe de Salcedo and Andrés de Urdaneta. In 1565 they established a practical east-west sailing route across the Pacific that took advantage of winds and currents. It became one of the world's great trade routes. Europeans could now travel and trade regularly across all the oceans of the world.

The age of European exploration yielded enormous improvements in geographic knowledge, travel, and trade. It had darker results as well. Many of the peoples that Europeans "discovered" in other continents had their lives violently disrupted. Whole civilizations in the Americas were conquered and wiped out, and millions of Africans became merchandise in a growing international slave trade. Earlier historians presented a positive view of the colonizers and missionaries whose work followed on the heels of exploration. In recent years, scholars have instead portrayed the legacy of Renaissance exploration as cruelty, environmental destruction, and the inability of cultures to communicate. Both views contain elements of truth, and each is one-sided and incomplete without the other. For better or worse, the explorers of the European Renaissance brought the various branches of the human family together and laid the foundations of the modern world.

The revelation of America as a newly-discovered continent challenged fundamental aspects of the Renaissance worldview while introducing a new body of ideas and myths into European thought. The voyages of exploration provided materials for the printing presses of Europe and at the same time provided inspiration for the writers and poets of the late Renaissance. Strongly influential in shaping perceptions of the New World were the published diaries and letters of such explorers as Sir Walter Raleigh and Hernán Cortés, which documented the course of exploration voyages and the characteristics of the new land and its inhabitants. The literary outgrowths of these popular writings included the expansion of travel literature, fictional genres including the imaginary voyage and the prose romance, and the imaginary societies depicted in Renaissance Utopian literature.

Contemporary critics have noted that Renaissance exploration chronicles are characterized by the imposition of European images and values onto an unfamiliar world—explorers often recorded only what they expected to see, overlooking or severely altering features of the American landscape and Native American culture for which they had no familiar reference point. The Christian tradition, for example, contributed to the early conception of America as an Edenic land populated by "peaceful and innocent children", free from the corruption of material possessions and government. Conversely, as conflicts arose between Europeans and Natives, Indians were widely regarded as "children of Satan" who symbolized the dangerous implications of a world free of law or religion. It may reasonably be suggested, therefore, that no study of the Renaissance is complete without a consideration of the simultaneous world exploration.

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